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Why the *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions* asks authors to include the country name in the title

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Kate Wilson,¹ in response to Dee Knipe and Rachel Jewkes,² made some interesting points about whether the country name should be included in the title of research articles. In my field of parasitology, I find it convenient to know in which country a parasitology study was done when choosing whether to read the abstract. However, this information is often not available, in particular, when studies were done in the United States.

I have been the editor of the *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions* (eISSN: 1975-5937, <https://jeehp.org>, *JEEHP*) since 2005. Through 2014, *JEEHP* did not implement a consistent policy regarding the inclusion of the country name in the title. Since 2015, I have asked authors to add the country name of the study population to the title because the cultural background is essential information for health education. If an article contains any research data, adding the country name to the title is mandatory. Based on my experience as an editor, I would like to address the three questions posed in Kate Wilson's piece.¹

Should all papers include country information in their titles?

Knipe and Jewkes² recommended that authors include the name of the country in which human studies were conducted in the report title. I agree with their recommendation. Their other recommendation, 'when previously conducted studies are reported, authors should highlight the context in which the studies originate', is essential. I previously did not recognise the importance of this kind of description, and I will accept this recommendation immediately in my journal.

How important is country information when evaluating a paper?

The country name may attract the interest of readers from the same country. Although

I am unaware of any evidence, it is reasonable to conjecture that readers would be particularly interested in articles from their own countries, so including this in the title would facilitate assessment and literature searches. The inclusion of the country name may not influence reviewers. The introduction of reporting guidelines to the peer review process means that determining the scientific soundness of an article becomes a systematic task based on compliance with the relevant guidelines for a specific study design. In reporting guidelines, country information of human study is usually mandated in the setting section.

How can bias against research carried out in certain countries be addressed?

The *JEEHP* has adopted a single-anonymised peer review system. To the best of my judgement, I could not find any instances of peer reviewers' bias based on the country name in the title or the author's country of affiliation in my journal, although I have actively looked at all reviewers' comments. If an editor thinks that a reviewer is affected by bias concerning the country of the study population or the author's country, the editor can address this issue by revising reviewers' comments after negotiation with them. In fact, it is the editor's responsibility to remove the impact of reviewers' biases regarding the country of the authors by revision or by seeking different reviewers.

In conclusion, based on my experiences as the long-term editor of *JEEHP*, I believe Knipe and Jewkes'² recommendation for including the country name in the title shall be an excellent guideline to clarify the cultural background of human population studies. I began propagating this guideline to my colleague editors in Korea.

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2. Knipe D, Jewkes R. Equity in reporting settings of studies. *ESE*. 2022;48:e87545. [CrossRef]

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